

3D visualization of micrometer sized structures in technical materials via Micro-CT and FIB/SEM - with tomographic datasets and video files of a microfluidic probe -

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Abstract

This is a method and application note, in which we present one of our works on the characterization of interior structures via μ -CT (micro-computed tomography) and FIB/SEM (focused ion beam/scanning electron microscopy). As an example, we selected the characterization of a microfluidic device (probe). Both μ -CT (micro-tomography) and FIB/SEM cross sectioning methods are applied.

For the μ -CT part, the main workflow includes:

- μ -CT scanning (creating projection x-ray shadow images in different angles)
- tomographic data processing and
- 3D tomographic visualization.

The μ -CT is a prioritized tomography method, especially when micrometer sized structures are the main interest. Thanks to the well-developed instruments and software, the method is quite straightforward. The machine takes a series of x-ray shadow images by rotating the object by 360° or 180° in free selectable steps. This set of pictures is then reconstructed into a new set of tomographic slices. However, we find that the post-processing work on the tomography datasets remains quite challenging.

The objective of this work is the 3D visualization, which gives us a direct deeper look into the interior of the material and the structure. One of these post processing works is the segmentation, which specifies different structural or material components within the tomography dataset. After a successful segmentation, we colored and visualized the structures in 3D, which is described in detail for our example below.

For the FIB/SEM part, we simply present cross-sectional images showing resolutions beyond the limit of the μ -CT method. While μ -CT shows a resolution limit in micrometer dimensions, the FIB/SEM method is able to resolve structures down to a few nanometers and supplies therefore finer structural details. On the other hand, FIB-SEM with a gallium ion beam is quite limited to the characterization of small selected areas, especially compared to μ -CT, which gives us a large structural overview in 3D. Therefore, both methods complement each other very well.

It is also possible to get sectional tomographic (3D) visualizations via FIB/SEM, but this method is quite time consuming and would give only very little additional information for our example. Therefore, this was not the aim of this work. However, we applied this method in the characterization of other materials, where micrometer-to-nanometer sized 3D structure were our main interest. These works will be reported later.

Material

The microfluidic probe was designed and fabricated in the research group of Dr. Ruther. For fabrication details and electrophysiological applications in a laboratory test, please refer to the original research paper of the group [1].

The probe is mainly composed of a Si base, an etched micro channel, deposited SiO_x/SiN_y multi layers as dielectric and stress-compensating coating. There are Au containing conductive paths embedded in SiO_x/SiN_y layers. On top surface, there are Ir containing coatings/pads, which interconnect to the embedded Au conductive paths. All these metal components belongs to the microelectronics of the microfluidic device [1].

Methods

1) micro-CT scanning: projection (shadow) images

The micro-CT allows to scan an object with a 180° or 360° rotation. X-ray shadow images can be taken with free selectable angle steps of usually 0.1° up to 0.5°, depending on the resolution needed. We used a **Bruker SkyScan 1272** (operated in the Core Facility “Imaging of Materials Systems”) to scan the needle-like probe. The instrument uses a micro focused X-ray beam with a spot size smaller than 5µm. For the X-ray source we selected a voltage of 50 kV and a current of 200 µA.

The probe sample was mounted upright in the µ-CT scanner with the rotation axis along (although not 100% exactly) the length of the probe. Now the scanning strategy and parameters should be optimized. In case of this study, we used 0.1° rotation steps and a 360° total rotation. A “post-scan” with a large rotation step was added to check and correct the small image drifts during the slow scan process. This was used later in the reconstruction step (s. below). After starting the scan, 3600 projection images were taken automatically. As an example, Fig. 1 shows one of these projection images. The image pixel size was set to be 625 nm/pixel.

A complete raw dataset of the projection images (images in tif format and with 16 bit grayscale) has a data size of more than 5 GB in zip-format and we will not deposit it in Zenodo due to its too large size but keep it locally at the authors:

FprobeIL00003599.zip

Projection images may only be interesting for readers, who want to reconstruct them into tomographic dataset by using certain software or algorithms, other than the NRecon method presented below. The most material researchers are only interested in the reconstructed results.

Fig. 1: An x-ray shadow image of the microfluidic probe.

2) 3D-Reconstruction

We used Bruker **NRecon 1.6.10** in combination with **InstaRecon** (reconstruction server/engine) to reconstruct the series of projection images into a tomographic image stack. Post alignments were executed, which means, the projection images taken by slow rotation were shifted according to the quick scans (scan with a large rotation step).

After initial reconstruction, the tomographic data set must be further processed, as the probe axis in the tomographic data set was not perfectly oriented in the z direction. This was due to imperfect mounting of the probe with a small tilting angle (see the shadow image Fig. 1). To correct this we used Bruker software **DataViewer** and its 3D registration function, by rotate/tilt the axes and resample the tomographic data set. The result (complete dataset) is now uploaded here (in multipage tif format):

FProbe_3D_Rec.tif

A multipage tif (tiff) file could be opened with, e.g., Irfanview, Fiji (ImageJ) or Avizo/Amira etc.

3) Tomographic image segmentation

The Micro-CT dataset obtained in **2)** is a stack of grayscale images. Fig. 2 shows one of the (cross) sections (position refer to Fig 6). The brightness represents the electron density of the respective materials (components). The brightness of the elements increases in the following order: air, O/N, Si, Au/Ir/Ti/Pt. Note: the object surface appears typically brighter.

Fig. 2: Cross section - a slice from the micro-CT tomography dataset (ref. FProbe_3D_Rec.tif). The red rectangular part shows the microfluidic channel. For the FIB/SEM cross sectioning method (see Fig. 4a and 4b), the position of this cross section is shown in Fig. 6.

That is why we can clearly recognize, in Fig. 2, the dark channel (air) and the bright Ir containing component topping the surface. However, the other components containing SiOx/SiNy, Si and Au are just faintly recognizable by respective grayscales. To distinguish and separate all these 5 components within the tomographic data set, we used the open source software **ILASTIK** [2], an interactive learning and segmentation toolkit, and its pixel classification tool (ref. to: ilastik.org), which proved to be very effective in 3D segmentation. The software has a quite easy-to-use 'learning from training data' interface. Once the classifier has been trained on a few 2D slices or a small subset of data, it can automatically classify all voxels in the volume with a very high matching quote.

5 Probability maps and segmented CT dataset in 8-bit grayscale of the 5 respective components could be thereafter generated. The resulting Files in multipage TIFF format are uploaded here:

Channel.tif

Si.tif

SiOxSiNy.tif

Au.tif

Ir.tif

These files have again multipage tif-format. The Voxel size of these data sets are 625 nm/voxel.

After segmentation, the different components could be colored and later visualized by Avizo software. (ref. below).

As an example, Fig. 3 shows the segmented microfluidic-channel as one component.

Fig. 3: Segmented microfluidic-channel.

4) 3D-Visualization of the μ -CT result

Avizo for EM Systems - Materials Science V 9.5.0 was used to make the 3D visualization. Herewith one could create different kind of 3D visualization. Fig 4 gives an example, where certain materials could be removed to unveil the structure below them.

Fig. 4: Avizo processed 3D visualization. The segmented components are colored in green, blue, gray, yellow and orange for Si, channel, SiOx, Au/Ti and Ir respectively. Different parts with components removed to show structures beneath them.

The result can be even better illustrated in a Video uploaded here. File is in mpeg format:

microfluid_device_2.mpeg

5) FIB/SEM cross-sectioning images

As described above, the recording of tomography datasets with a well-developed micro-CT is a quite easy-to-use method. However, it has, in comparison to FIB/SEM, a resolution limit in the micrometer size. The FIB/SEM images reveals more and finer structure details.

The FIB/SEM method (used instrument: FEI Scios 2 HiVac) was applied to make a cross section imaging (Fig. 5a and 5b). The position of this cross section could be identified in the SEM overview image (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5: a Cross section imaged with FIB/SEM, the image is tilted to 45°. This cross section area corresponds to the μ -CT cross section shown in the red frame in Fig. XX. The channel seen here in the FIB/SEM image could also be seen by the micro-CT method; b: zoomed from a. The images are tilted to 45° without aspect correction.

In Fig. 5a and 5b the alternative SiO_x/NO_x multilayer (stack) and the Au conductive paths cross sectioned by Ga ion beam could be clearly seen. These structure could not be resolved with the micro-CT method.

6) Correlation of μ -CT and FIB/SEM

Fig. 6 shows a SEM image of the probe. The sample was fixed on silver paste

Fig 6. SEM overview of the microfluidic probe. The positions of the micro-CT cross section slice in Fig. 1 and FIB/SEM cross section in Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b are marked in red.

Fig 7. Micro-CT, segmented and depicted with all components; Comparable to the SEM overview image in Fig. 6.

The electrical conduction paths within the device made of Au/Ti could be resolved

Fig. 8: A) SEM image electrical conduction paths (lines) sealed by SiOx/NOx multilayers and open electrode (bright circle) for contact. B) corresponding micro-CT image, segmented and with SiOx/NOx removed.

Fig. 9: comparison of FIB/SEM and μ-CT results: cross section of the micro fluidic channel

Note, the different brightness of the various materials in the SEM and the μ -CT are both based on electron density in the different materials. The electron beam with an accelerating voltage of 20 – 30 kV can penetrate the sample surface down to a few micron meters in depth, whereas X-Ray can go through the whole sample. In the SEM this material contrast is combined with the “topographical information” resulting from the formation of SE electrons. In the μ -CT we make use of the x-ray Shadow picture series and reconstruction to get tomographical measurements.

References

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- [2] Berg, S., Kutra, D., Kroeger, T. et al. “ilastik: interactive machine learning for (bio) image analysis”. Nat Methods 16, 1226–1232 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0582-9>